

TITLE- Keesing's Asia News Digest

1st EDITION- 1955 onwards

PUBLISHER- Keesing's worldwide LLC

PLACE OF PUBLICATION- U.S.A, *London*

FREQUENCY- Weekly

INTRODUCTION

Keesing's Asia News Digest offers one unique and efficient way to stay informed about the vital events shaping Asia each month. Asian news digest, formerly Asian recorder 1955-1999 is a comprehensive weekly journal on Asian and world affairs. Asian digest was launched at the dawn of the millennium 1st January, 2000 as successor to the Asian recorder. Keesing's Asia News Digest enables one to focus on conducting business, official duties and research. As the digest provides reporting upon which one can rely.

Keesing's Asia News Digest is a venue whereby users may access Keesings World News Archive (Archive). The Archive is a web-based database, comprises all of the articles that have published from 1931-1987 as Keesings Contemporary Archives and then as Keesings Record of World Events from 1987 to the present.

SCOPE

- It is designed for scholars, diplomats, business people and government officials, as it make them stay completely and accurately informed about the events in Asia.
- It Covers Southern, Eastern, Central and South-Eastern Asia as well as Oceania. Each edition focuses on elections, appointments, registrations, government changes, natural and man-made disasters, national budgets, economic developments, foreign relations, social issues and conflicts.
- Keesing's editorial process developed over 80 years of publishing Keesing's Contemporary Archive and Record of World Events, which proven to deliver accurate, objective and comprehensive coverage of political, social and economic events.

TREATMENT

1. It has separate columns of highlights describing major events.
2. A chart representing 44 Asian countries along with their population, area (sq.km) and capitals are given in the beginning.
3. Brief description regarding events occurred in a country is given citing name of newspaper, its date and page number.
4. Column regarding global concerns issues and challenges are provided.
5. Information is collected from leading newspapers and journals of Asia and top ranking international dailies.

ARRANGEMENT

1. It is arranged region wise alphabetically, within each region countries are arranged in alphabetical order.
2. On the top of the margins date regarding coverage of events is given.
3. It has an annual index, compiles in a country subject wise format to help the user gain instant access to the million word annual data annual volume comprising all the 52 issues of the year.

FORMAT

Asian news digest is available in print, eBook and kindle.

Print Features

- Quality of paper is good
- Printing is clear and legible
- It is given in 3 column per page

eBook Features

- It is a replica of the print version
- 1st January, 2000 onwards entire text of print version is available in eBook format.

CONCLUSION

It is one of the most important and useful source of information. It provides up to date information. It covers national and international issues and demand. It is quite simply, the best and most effective way to be well informed about Asia's current affairs.

REFERENCES

- <https://www.overdrive.com/series/keesings-asia-news-digest>
- https://www.amazon.in/Keesings-Asia-News-Digest-December-ebook/dp/B006L7IBMU/ref=sr_1_1?keywords=keesing%27s+asia+news+digest&qid=1572774151&sr=8-1